

Analogue of Chloramphenicol—Part IV. Synthesis and Biological activity of 2-Dichloroacetamido-1-(4-chloro-3-nitrophenyl)propane-1, 3-diol and Biological activity of 2-Dichloroacetamido-1-(4-bromo-3-nitrophenyl)propane-1, 3-diol

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3-Nitro-4-chloro- α -aminoacetophenone hydrochloride III on treatment with 2,2'-dichloroacetyl chloride yields the corresponding α -dichloroacetamido derivative (IV). Hydroxymethylation of IV followed by Meerwein-Ponndorf-Verley reduction yields the desired chloramphenicol analogue, dl-threo-2-dichloroacetamido-1-(4-chloro-3-nitrophenyl)-propane-1,3-diol (VI).

THE chemical stability and ready synthesis of chloramphenicol as well as the relative simplicity of its structure make this antibiotic a popular model for studying the effect of variations in structure on biological activity. A large number of analogues of chloramphenicol have been prepared and studied in biological system. Various compounds related to chloramphenicol have been tested for their antibacterial activities with respect to the parent chloramphenicol and found that only the D-threo-2-dichloroacetamido-1, 3-propane diol moiety is essential to the activity and the optimum biological activity is dependent upon the electron rich substituents in the aromatic rings¹. While studying the structural modifications on the biological activity of chloramphenicol, Buu-Hoi *et al.*, found that antibacterial properties of chloramphenicol were qualitatively connected with the three-configuration of the molecule and the presence of a para substituent in the position of the phenyl nucleus rather than with the nature of the substituent².

Taking into consideration the above experimental facts and as a part of our programme in the continued search for new antibacterial agents³, we prepared the analogues of chloramphenicol in which both nitro and chloro groups are present in the aromatic ring.

The title compound has been synthesised starting from 4-chloro-3-nitroacetophenone⁷ following exactly the method for the preparation of the corresponding 4-bromo compound³.

Bromination of 3-nitro-4-chloroacetophenone(I) in the α -position gave α -bromo acetophenone derivative II which on treatment with hexamethylenetetramine followed by the hydrolysis of the quaternary salt with alcoholic hydrochloric acid at room temperature yielded α -amino-4-chloro-3-nitroacetophenone hydrochloride which was then treated with α ,

α' -dichloroacetyl chloride at 80° to give the corresponding dichloroacetamide IV. Hydroxymethylation of IV was accomplished in ethanolic solution using 37-38% aqueous formaldehyde and sodium bicarbonate. The resulting 2-dichloroacetamido-3-hydroxy-1-(4-chloro-3-nitrophenyl)-1-propanone V was converted to the desired dl-threo-2-dichloroacetamido-1-(4-chloro-3-nitrophenyl)propane-1,3-diol (VI) using Meerwein-Ponndorf-Verley reduction.

Analogues of bromo derivative have been tested for their antibacterial activities. The bacteria used were *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *D. sonnei*, Paratyphoid "A" and Paratyphoid "B".

From the above observations, we can conclude that the introduction of a bromine atom in the para position and also shifting the nitro group to the meta position with respect to propane diol moiety, considerably increases the antibacterial activity. The results are tabulated in the Table 1.

2-Dichloroacetamido-1-(4-chloro-3-nitrophenyl)-propane-1,3-diol compound including the intermediates involved in the synthesis were screened for antimicrobial activity. None of these compounds exhibited significant activity.

2-Dichloroacetamido-1-(4-chloro-3-nitrophenyl)-propane-1,3-diol was synthesised according to Caldwell and Schweiker's method⁵, resolved and screened for the antimicrobial activity. It was observed that the title compound including the intermediates obtained by the above method⁵ showed no significant activity⁸.

Experimental

4-Chloro-3-nitro- α -aminoacetophenone hydrochloride (III):

Powdered hexamethylene tetramine (0.67 mole) mixed with dry chlorobenzene (570 ml) was added

TABLE I—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY BY CUP-PLATE METHOD

Micro-organisms : (i) *S. aureus*
 (ii) *D. sonnei*
 (iii) Paratyphoid "A"
 (iv) Paratyphoid "B"
 and (v) *E. coli*
 (a) Drug concentration : 10 mg./ml. of ethanol or DMF
 (b) Quantity in each cup : 0.1 ml.
 (c) Diameter of the cup : 10 mm.
 (d) Positive Control : (i) 5% Phenol soln. in water
 (ii) Chloramphenicol 10 µg. in H₂O

S. No.	Name of the Compound	Zone of Inhibition														
		<i>S. aureus</i>			<i>D. sonnei</i>			Paratyphoid "A"			Paratyphoid "B"			<i>E. coli</i>		
		Hours	24	48	Hours	24	48	Hours	24	48	Hours	24	48	Hours	24	48
1.	3-Nitro-4-bromo- α -dichloroacetamido-acetophenone	24	48	72	24	48	72	24	48	72	24	48	72	24	48	72
		-	-	1+	-	-	18+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	2-Dichloroacetamido-3-hydroxy-1-(3-nitro-4-bromophenyl)-1-propanone	26+	27+	26+	25+	25+	28+	-	-	30+	-	17+	19+	-	-	-
3.	di-threo-2-dichloroacetamido-1-(3-nitro-4-bromophenyl)propane-1,3-diol	30+	39+	38+	40+	40+	16±	-	-	41+	-	33+	41+	-	-	31+
4.	3-Nitro-4-bromo- α -acetamido-acetophenone	-	-	11+	-	19+	47+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	3-Nitro-4-bromo- α -acetamido- α' -hydroxypropionophenone	28+	31+	28+	30+	30+	28+	-	-	22+	-	26+	25+	-	-	-
6.	di-threo-1-(3-nitro-4-bromophenyl)-2-acetamido-1,3-propane diol	15±	16+	16+	19(SI)	23+	23±	-	-	-	-	-	14+	-	-	11+
		22+	22+	21+	20+	20+	19+	-	-	-	-	-	-	21+	21+	20+
		29+	29+	27+	20+	21+	21+	-	-	-	-	-	-	26+	27+	26+
		16+	16+	16+	16+	16+	16+	-	-	-	-	-	-	16+	16+	16+

Positive Control :

- i) Phenol (5% soln. in H₂O)
- ii) Chloramphenicol (10 µg in H₂O)
- iii) Solvent control (a) Alcohol (b) DMF

+ = indicates complete inhibition; ± = indicates partial inhibition; SI = Slight inhibition; - = No inhibition

in one lot to a solution of 4-chloro-3-nitroacetophenone⁷ (0.61 mole) in dry chlorobenzene 570 (ml). Immediately a thick mixture was obtained which was slowly heated to raise the temperature 50°–52°, where it was maintained by external heating for four hours. The slurry matter which was obtained after stirring was cooled to 30°, filtered, and the residue was again stirred with 400 ml of ethanol, filtered again and washed with 100 ml of ethanol. This process was repeated several times. The product was dried in vacuo over calcium chloride, m.p. 162°–64° (decomp.). Yield 80%.

The hexamethylene salt (0.2 mole) obtained above was added to ethanolic hydrochloric acid (175/85 ml). The suspension thus obtained was continuously stirred at room temperature for sixteen hours. Then the mixture was cooled to 5° and filtered. The solid product obtained consists of amine hydrochloride and ammonium chloride, was stirred for 15 minutes with 100 ml of water at 25°, cooled to 10° and filtered. The product was dried in vacuo over calcium chloride, m.p. 210°–12° (decomp.); yield 70%.

4-Chloro-3-nitro- α -dichloroacetamido acetophenonic (IV)

The product III (2.51 g; 0.01 mole) and α , α' -dichloroacetyl chloride (10 ml) was stirred for 30 mins. at 80°. The reaction mixture was cooled and decomposed into 50 ml of ice-cold water when IV separated out. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol in pale yellow shining needles; m.p. 128°; yield 2.0 g. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_7Cl_2N_2O_4$: C, 36.86; H, 2.1. Found: C, 36.87; H, 2.5%.

2-Dichloroacetamido-3-hydroxy-1-(4-chloro-3-nitrophenyl)-1-propanone (V)

A suspension of 1.8 g (0.0057 mole) of 4-chloro-3-nitro- α -dichloroacetamidoacetophenone in 5 ml of 37–38% aqueous formaldehyde and 20 ml of 95% ethanol containing a small amount of sodium bicarbonate was stirred at room temperature for 2 hours. The mixture was poured in ice-water and the solid separated was filtered, washed with water two to three times and dried to give 1.6 g of 2-dichloroacetamido-3-hydroxy-1-(4-chloro-3-nitrophenyl)-1-propanone. It was recrystallised from dilute ethanol in pale yellow needles; m.p. 95°–96°; yield 1.5 g. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_9Cl_2N_2O_5$: C, 38.18; H, 2.45; Found: C, 37.57; H, 2.60%.

dl-threo-2-Dichloroacetamido-1-(4-chloro-3-nitrophenyl)-propane-1,3-diol (VI)

To a hot solution of aluminumisopropoxide (1.89) in dry isopropyl alcohol (15 ml) was added compound V (1.25 g) in a 50 ml flask equipped with a Han's

condenser. After few minutes an opaque red-brown solution was formed and at the same time the removal of acetone was continued for four hours at which time the acetone test was negative. At the end of the reaction distillation was rapid.

The thick red-brown residue was allowed to cool just below the reflux temperature and 5 ml of water was added. The mixture was refluxed for about 15 mins. and filtered. During refluxing the colour changed to light yellow. The residue was refluxed with aqueous isopropyl alcohol (25 ml; 80%) for about 10 mins. The extract was concentrated in vacuo, the residue refluxed with ethylacetate (25 ml) until the oily material had dissolved. The isopropyl alcohol was removed under reduced pressure, the pasty material thus obtained passed through an activated alumina column using ethylacetate-petroleum ether (60°–80°) (1 : 7) as an eluent. The fractions which gave a crystalline solid were combined and recrystallised from petroleum ether (60°–80°) to give 300 mg of light yellow crystals; m.p. 120°–121°. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{11}Cl_2N_2O_6$: C, 36.85; H, 2.90; Found: C, 36.91; H, 3.07%.

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